

Grain yield and yield components of rice as influenced by different crop establishment methods

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Conventional methods of rice transplanting have become expensive because of increasing cost of seed, fertilizer, water, and labor. A system of rice intensification (SRI), introduced from Madagascar (Uphoff 2006), and its improved form, integrated crop management (ICM), need to be further evaluated. During a national symposium on SRI held in November 2006 at ANGRAU, Hyderabad, India, farmers from Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu claimed great savings in terms of seed, water, and labor with SRI. To validate these claims, an experiment was conducted to evaluate different crop establishment methods in the Tarai plain of Uttarakhand.

A field experiment was conducted during the wet seasons of 2005 and 2006 at Pantnagar (29° N, 79°29' E, 243.8 m), Uttarakhand. Six and eight crop establishment methods were tested in 2005 and 2006, respectively. Only four methods were discussed here: SRI with a spacing of 25 × 25 cm, one 9-d-old seedling per hill; ICM with 20 × 20-cm spacing, two 15-d-old seedlings per hill; line sowing of sprouted seeds at 20-cm distance in puddled soil; and the conventional method of transplanting (20 × 10-cm spacing, two 25-d-old seedlings per hill). The soil of the experimental field is Aquic Hapludoll, silty loam in texture, and rich in organic carbon (1.15%), and it has medium phosphorus (20.3 kg ha⁻¹ Olsen's

P) and potash (222 kg ha⁻¹) levels.

Rainfall received during the crop period was 1,725 mm in 2005 and 802 mm in 2006. The experimental field has been under a rice-wheat rotation system since 1966. The high-yielding variety Pant Dhan 4 was used in the experiment, which had a randomized block design with five replications. In addition to inorganic nutrients (120 kg N, 26.4 kg P, and 33.2 kg K), farmyard manure at 5 t ha⁻¹ was also added to the SRI and ICM plots. The SRI and ICM plots were kept moist up to the panicle initiation stage; water level was then maintained at 3–5 cm through the milk stage. The moist condition was maintained by providing irrigation during rainless periods and excess water was drained as and when needed. In SRI and ICM, weeds were controlled through a conoweeder (used 20, 45, and 55 d after transplanting). Weeds growing near the rice plants were manually removed. Grain yields

were adjusted to 14% moisture.

The grain yields obtained from the different crop establishment methods did not differ significantly. The number of tillers and panicles m⁻² recorded with direct seeding was significantly higher than that observed in SRI, ICM, and conventional transplanting, except for number of tillers produced under conventional transplanting in 2005. The SRI produced 12 panicles (2005) and 14 panicles (2006) per hill as compared with five panicles per hill in conventional transplanting. SRI tiller number was statistically on a par with ICM in both years. The number of filled grains per panicle was highest in SRI (117). SRI and ICM were found to save irrigation water by about 50% compared with conventional transplanting and line sowing of sprouted seeds in puddled soil. SRI and ICM also had 80% and 57% savings on seed rate (Table 2). However, these results need to be evaluated further.

Table 1. Grain yield and yield components as influenced by crop establishment method.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Panicles m ⁻² (no.)		Tillers m ⁻² (no.)		Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	
	2005	2006	2005	2006	2005	2006	2005	2006
Conventional transplanting	6.52	6.22	227	246	363	353	101	96
System of rice intensification	5.84	6.65	187	217	266	286	104	117
Integrated crop management	5.93	6.41	222	234	278	325	100	102
Direct seeding (line sowing)	5.79	6.11	290	328	415	414	71	73
SE	0.34	0.20	17	11	24	20	4	4
LSD 0.05	ns	ns	54	33	77	60	14	11

Reference

Uphoff N. 2006. Thoughts on the history, principles of SRI, and its importance for the present scenario. Paper presented at the National Symposium on SRI—Present Status and Future Prospects, 17-18 Nov. 2006, Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, India.

Table 2. Number of irrigations and seeding rate used in both 2005 and 2006 wet seasons.

Treatment	Irrigations (no.)	Seeding rate (kg ha ⁻¹)
Conventional transplanting	12	35
System of rice intensification	6	7
Integrated crop management	6	15
Direct seeding (line sowing)	12	50

